

ISSUES OF CRIMINAL LIABILITY APPLIED TO PERSONS UNDER THE AGE OF 18 IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. According to our national legislation, persons under the age of 18 are considered minors. In our country, special attention is paid to protecting the rights and legal interests of minors, to creating all the conditions for them to grow up as fully-fledged individuals. This article analyzes issues of criminal liability applied to persons under the age of 18 in Uzbekistan.

Keywords: Constitution, law, punishments, conviction, offence.

The duty of minors is the obligation of people who have committed a wrongdoing beneath the age of 18, entirely constrained sorts of discipline endorsed by the criminal law. Specific characteristics of crimes committed by minors in the criminal law of the Republic of Uzbekistan, etc. taking into account the circumstances, special responsibility is determined. These are: a) fine; b) correctional works; c) imprisonment; g) is one of the punishments of deprivation of liberty. They are assigned depending on the type and nature of the crime, and other types of punishment, additional punishments cannot be assigned to minors. The amount and terms of punishment imposed on persons who committed crimes before reaching adulthood have been significantly reduced. Correctional work from 1 month to 1 year. is determined within the period of up to 10 days, and it is not possible to send the prisoner to places other than his place of residence to serve this sentence. The term of imprisonment is from 1 to 3 months. The term of deprivation of liberty is also determined depending on the age of minors and the degree of social danger of the crime: it is up to 3 years for those under 16 years old for a less serious crime; for a serious crime - up to 6 years; for a very serious crime - up to 10 years; 16 to 18-year-olds - up to 4 years for a less serious crime; up to 7 years for a serious crime; for a very serious crime - up to 10 years, and these terms cannot be deviated from in any case. Adolescents who have been sentenced to detention by the court will serve their sentence in an Adolescent Remedial Colony. Extraordinary rules for the exception of minors from risk or discipline apply. Conviction is a legal status resulting from the fact that a person has been convicted of a crime. A person is considered to have been convicted from the date of entry into legal force of the conviction on which the punishment was imposed. A person released from

punishment by the court is considered not convicted. In connection with the expiration of the term of the conviction or the removal of the conviction, all its legal consequences are null and void. Also, if it is determined that the state of conviction ends with the completion of the sentence for the committed crime, the person is considered not convicted.

The main tasks of prevention of delinquency and delinquency among minors are as follows:

- ✓ prevention of unsupervised, careless, delinquency or other antisocial behavior by minors, identification and elimination of reasons and conditions that enable them;
- ✓ ensuring the protection of the rights, freedoms and legal interests of minors;
- ✓ formation of law-abiding behavior in minors;
- ✓ socio-pedagogical rehabilitation of minors and families in a socially dangerous situation;
- ✓ to identify and eliminate cases of involvement of minors in committing crimes or other antisocial behavior.

Offenses committed by minors and other anti-social behavior, evading or improperly fulfilling their obligations to provide, raise and educate minors, or have a negative impact on their behavior keeps an account of parents or substitute parents who influence or abuse them, and also collects and summarizes the information necessary to compile a statistical report. People who draw in minors to commit wrongdoings or other introverted behavior or commit other unlawful acts against minors, as well as from satisfying their commitments to supply, raise and teach minors Recognizes guardians or substitutes for guardians who are sidestepping or coming up short to comply appropriately, or who have a negative affect on the behavior of minors or who treat them pitilessly, and take activity against them as given for by law. submits proposition to pertinent state bodies and other organizations on the application of mystery measures. An ask to expand the period of detainment of a minor in a social-legal help center and materials affirming the require for an expansion of this period should be submitted by the head of the social-legal help center or his agent. might be sent to the locale (city) court at slightest three days some time recently the conclusion of the period of keeping the minor within the social-legal help center.

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